

EFFECTIVENESS OF AUDIO-VISUAL PRESENTATION ON THE PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 6 LEARNING IN ARLING PANLIPUNAN

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Abstract. The study aimed to determine the effectiveness of audio-visual presentations on the performance of Grade 6 learners in Araling Panlipunan. In this study, learners in the Control group obtained a mean of 17.85 and the Experimental group obtained a mean of 24.64 during their post-test. Both groups actually improved in their performance but the performance of the Experimental group was much higher than the Control group with the former being exposed to the use of audio-visual presentation in the teaching of Araling Panlipunan to the Grade 6 learners. There is a significant difference in the performance of grade 6 learners in Araling Panlipunan along the topics in fourth quarter after the exposure of audiovisual presentation in teaching Araling Panlipunan 6. Using the audio-visual presentation in teaching Araling Panlipunan 6, the performance of Grade 6 learners can be improved and changed for the better.

Keywords. Audio-visual presentation, Araling Panlipunan, Grade 6, effectiveness, performance

1 Introduction

The teacher-researcher believes that Araling Panlipunan should be part of the curriculum for the purpose of helping students understand human interactions that occurred in the past, are occurring now, and that are likely to occur in the future. The reason for these understandings is that they may help students develop and nurture values that will make it more likely that they will be able to determine for any situation what the right thing is and do it, especially when doing the right thing is hard to do.

According to former Education Secretary Br. Armin B. Luistro, the new curriculum is focused more on the learners and not on the teacher. Luistro said, "It is not enough that we merely continue building classroom and toilets. The real revolution in education in which has long term effects can only be done through information technology.

The development of technology gives impact to the learning environment. A variety of modern learning tools and education facilities contribute to the optimization of the learning process, both at school and daily life and, offers many ranges of facility in learning (Flores, 2018).

The potential of the teacher to use technology enhances the teacher and students' thinking and develop the latter's eagerness to learn more about the subject. In this sense, Audio-visual presentation can be used fruitfully especially nowadays that K to 12 is in its full swing (Posadas, 2016). Indeed, technology equips teachers to teach with high quality content giving them enough time to explain difficult lessons. It is with this concept that the teacher-researcher believes that the use of audio-visual presentation nurtures the students in learning more about the different lessons in Araling Panlipunan subject.

The researcher being in the service for one year as administrative assistant and is about to enter into teaching as Araling Panlipunan teacher is aware of the dismal results of the students' performance in Araling Panlipunan in the previous periodical test. The mediocre academic performance of the learners is also evident in the results

posted in the National Achievement Test given by DepEd to Grade 7 in the year 2018 with an average of 52.8%. The result is far and below the criterion target set by the Department of Education which is 75%.

2 Review of Related Literature

The reviewed studies are contributory to the present study in one way or another. These studies provide information and ideas that contributed to the flow of the study that served as guide to the researcher. The present study is different from other studies reviewed since it has different subjects and research design. On the other hand, the studies of Herrera et. al (2014), Bustos (2015), and Mathew and Alidmat (2013) has similarities with the present study because the mentioned studies used audio-visual materials to enhance the performance of the learners.

While the studies of Flores (2018), Polk (2015), Abbot (2015), Brock and Joglekar (2014), Wang (2016), Chen & Sun (2014), Delos Santos (2016), and Cruz (2015) used educational videos, animations and PowerPoint presentations versus traditional instruction to test the performance of learners.

The studies of Massialas and Cox (2007), Enriquez (2009) and Anderson (2009) state that effective teaching calls for different teaching strategies. No teaching approach to teaching will work in all situations. The studies of Onasanya and Omeowo (2015) and Reyes (2017) used quasi-experimental method of research to compare computer-assisted intervention materials and employed pre-test and post-test to determine the effectiveness of the computer-assisted materials versus traditional teaching strategy.

Salandanan (2009) and Handa et. Al. (2013) state that using audio-visual materials stimulate more than one sense making the students more attentive and provides learners with opportunities to represent and express their prior knowledge

3 Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The researcher used the quasi-experimental method of research. It employed the two group's pretest/post-test design in which the experimental group was exposed to the audio-visual presentation while the control group was exposed to the traditional instruction. Comparisons were made before and after the intervention. The lessons using audio-visual presentation were conducted during Fourth Quarter.

3.2 Population and Sample Size

The subjects of this study were the Grade 6 students of Bayambang Central School during the school year 2018-2019 wherein the two sections were used in the study. The researcher who is a non-teaching personnel asked permission from the Araling Panlipunan focal person to use the two sections heterogeneously grouped she was handling in Grade 6 as the subjects of the study. The Grade 6- Martinez who got the head during toss-coin was assigned as experimental group exposed to audio-visual presentation and the Grade 6-Ocampo who got the tail was assigned as control group exposed to traditional instruction.

3.3 Statistical Treatment of Data

To attain valid and reliable results from the data that were gathered, appropriate statistical tools were used. To answer sub-problem number 1 focusing on the question "What is the level of performance in Araling Panlipunan of the two groups of Grade 6 learners based on the pre-test?" and for sub-problem number 3 focusing on the question "What is the level of performance of the learners exposed to traditional instruction and those exposed to audio-visual presentation as revealed by the post-test?" the Mean and Mean Percentage Scores were used. To

answer sub-problem number 2 focusing on the question “Is there a significant difference in the level of performance of the two groups in the pretest?” and for sub-problem 4 focusing on the question “Is there a significant difference in the level of performance of the two groups in the post-test?” t-test for independent groups or uncorrelated means was used. To answer sub-problem number 5, t-test for correlated means or dependent groups was used in determining the significant difference in the pretest and post-test within each of the two groups namely, control group and experimental group.

4 Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation of Data

4.1 Learners Mastery Level in Araling Panlipunan 6 Based on the Pre-Test

From the table 1, it shows that the learners in the experimental group obtained a mean score of 15.87 and mean percentage score of 39.675 in the pre-test in Araling Panlipunan 6. On the other hand, the learners in the control group have mean of 15.97 and the computed mean percentage score is 39.925. Seemingly the two groups are more or less of the same initial performance in terms of their mean scores and Mean Percentage Scores and their scores indicate low mastery of the subject based on the performance scale. This impression of the insignificant mean difference however, is tested using the t-test for independent samples.

Table 1. Pre-test Result of the Control and Experimental Group

Group	Mean	Mean Percentage Score (MPS)	Standard Deviation
Control Group	15.97	39.925	4.65
Experimental Group	15.87	39.675	4.53

Table 2 shows the mean difference of 0.10 of the pre-test results between the learners belonging to the control group and experimental group. The computed t-value of 0.0986 is less than the critical t-value of 1.67 at 0.05 level of significance with the $df=76$. It can be deduced that the initial performance of the learners are the same with respect to their mean scores. Thus, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between the performances of the learners is hereby accepted.

Table 2. Test of Significant Difference in the Performance of the Control and Experimental Group in the Pre-Test

Group	Mean	Mean Difference	Computed t-value	Significance	Decision
Control Group	15.97	0.10	0.0986	Not Significant	H_0 is Accepted
Experimental Group	15.87				

4.2 Learners Mastery Level in Araling Panlipunan 6 Based on the Post-Test

Table 3 shows that the learners in the control group obtained a mean score 17.85 and mean percentage score of 44.625 in the post test in Araling Panlipunan 6. The learners in the experimental group obtained a mean score of 24.64 in the post test in Araling Panlipunan 6 and the computed Mean Percentage Score of this group exposed to audio-visual presentation is 61.60.

Comparing these values from the entries in Table 2, it can be observed that both groups demonstrated a marked increase in their performance in the post test with the control group having a mean gain of 1.88 while the experimental group, a mean gain of 8.77 that also indicates that the experimental group are nearing mastery of the subject based on the performance scale while the control group remained in the low mastery level. It can also be observed that the difference in their post-test mean scores has increased. Whether these increases are significant or not, is revealed in the succeeding sections.

Table 3. Post-test Performance Result of the Control and Experimental Group

Group	Mean	Mean Percentage Score (MPS)	Standard Deviation
Control Group	17.85	44.625	4.91
Experimental Group	24.64	61.60	5.66

4.3 Difference in the Performance of the Control and Experimental Group in the Post-test

Table 4 shows the mean difference of 6.79 in the post-test results between the learners belonging to the control group and experimental group. The computed t-value of 5.66 is greater than the critical t-value of 1.67 at 0.05 level of significance with the $df=76$. Since the computed t - value is greater than the critical t - value; it means that there is significant difference between the performances of the experimental group of Grade 6 learners after using audio-visual presentation in the teaching of Araling Panlipunan. Both groups improved after teaching but the improvement is significantly greater in the experimental group.

Table 4. Test for Significance of the Difference in the Performance of the Control and Experimental Group in the Post- test N=78

Group	Mean	Mean Difference	Computed t-value	Significance	Decision
Control Group	17.85	6.79	5.66	*Significant	H_0 is Rejected
Experimental Group	24.64				

4.3 Difference in the Performance of the Control Group in the Pre- test and Post- Test

Given the data below, the computed t - value on the performance of the control group in Araling Panlipunan before and after using traditional instruction in 5.73 was greater than the tabular value of 1.697 at 0.05 level of significance with 38 degrees of freedom.

Table 5. Test for Significance of the Difference in the Performance of the Control Group in the Pre-test and Post-Test, N=39

Group	Mean	Mean Difference	Computed t-value	Significance	Decision
Control Group	15.97	1.88	5.73	*Significant	H_0 is Rejected
Experimental Group	17.85				

Therefore, there is a sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. It can be safely concluded then that there is a significant difference between the performances of the Control Group using traditional instruction in the teaching of Araling Panlipunan as revealed in the pre-test and post-test results. This further means that the control group has significantly improved in their performance in the post-test as compared with their pre-test performance.

4.4 Difference in the Performance of the Control Group in the Pre- test and Post- Test

Given the data above, the computed t - value on the performance of the pupils in Araling Panlipunan before and after using audio-visual presentations in teaching was 11.14. This value is greater than the tabular value of 1.697 at 0.0543 level of significance with 38 degrees of freedom. Therefore, there is a sufficient evidence to reject the

null hypothesis and accept the research hypothesis. It can be safely concluded then that there is a significant difference between the performances of the experimental group using audio-visual presentations in teaching Araling Panlipunan as revealed in the pre-test and post-test results, with their pre-test performance significantly higher than their pre-test performance. It should be recalled at this point that although both groups had significantly improved in their performance, the experimental group had a higher mean increase and the group improved from low mastery to nearing mastery level after exposure to the audio-visual presentations.

Table 6. Test of Significance of the Difference in the Performance of the Experimental Group in the Pre-test and post test, N=39

Group	Mean	Mean Difference	Computed t-value	Significance	Decision
Control Group	15.87	8.77	11.14	*Significant	H ₀ is Rejected
Experimental Group	24.62				

5 Conclusion and Recommendation

Prior to the conduct of the experiment, the control group had a higher mean score in the pre-test compared with the experimental group, however, the difference is negligible. There is no significant difference in the level of performance of the two groups in the pre-test. There was a higher improvement among the scores of those in the experimental group compared to those of the control group as revealed in the post-test. There is significant difference in the level of performance of the two groups in the post-test. This only means that the use of audio-visual presentation in the teaching of Araling Panlipunan contributed a lot on the performance of the respondents under the experimental group. There is a significant difference in the performance of each of the two groups as revealed in the pre-test and post-test results. With the data gathered, the use of audio-visual presentations is considered effective with the experimental group demonstrating a higher increase than those who did not use audio-visual presentations.

Computer-aided materials such as the use of audio-visual presentations should be employed as a teaching approach in teaching Araling Panlipunan Grade 6 learners. Teachers in other learning areas may also try to dwell on using audiovisual presentations in their respective learning areas. School Administrators should design training programs for teachers focused on the use of audio-visual presentations as a teaching approach.

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